

A STUDY ON FRACTURE MECHANISMS OF CFRP
BY ACOUSTIC EMISSION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

The conventional CFRP of unidirectional and three-directional carbon fibre composite laminates are investigated by tensile tests and measuring the AE waves. The fracture mechanisms of the composite materials are studied by an AE frequency analysis, as it is thought that such ordinary AE parameters as the AE event count, the AE amplitude and so on, can not define clearly the mechanisms. It is found that the results of fracture mechanisms of model CFRP by using an AE frequency spectrum is applicable to the conventional CFRP. However, it is considered that the frequency of 630 KHz, which is not generated in the AE frequency spectrum of model CFRP, is generated by friction between the fibres on the fracture surfaces of the conventional CFRP.

INTRODUCTION

Recently FRP are widely used in various types of machines and a variety of structures. In order to maintain the safety of the machines and the structures, it is necessary to investigate the fracture mechanisms of FRP. The fracture process of FRP is so complicated that it seems difficult to measure accurately, but the acoustic emission (AE) method is effective for investigating and watching the fracture process of FRP [1].

Generally, the AE event count, the AE event rate, the AE energy, the AE amplitude and the frequency spectrum are used as the AE parameters and the fracture process is discussed by using these parameters. These parameters can give a clue for evaluation of the fracture toughness [2]. The AE event, the AE event rate, the AE energy and the AE amplitude are used as the ordinary AE parameters. However, the frequency spectrum is used in the frequency analysis. The fracture patterns of the conventional and laminated CFRP are studied by these AE parameters.

So, the AE signals are detected during the fracture process and also the macro- and micro-fracture surfaces are observed. Then, the selection of the parameters that can explain clearly the fracture process is studied by using the results obtained previously for the fracture mechanisms of the epoxy resin and the model CFRP [3], i.e. the unidirectional fibre reinforced and the cross fibre reinforced epoxy plastics, whose carbon fibres with a 2 mm distance are arranged in a single laminate.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Test materials

The specimens are made from carbon fibre and epoxy resin as conventional and laminated specimens. The specimens of $(0^\circ)_8$, $(45^\circ)_8$ and $(90^\circ)_8$ of the unidirectional fibre composite laminate are prepared, where the 0° shows the angle between the fibre direction and the load one, and the suffix "8" shows the numbers of laminates. These specimens are named C-1, C-2 and C-3, respectively. The specimen thickness is about 1 mm and the fibre content in the volume is about 55%, respectively. The specimens of $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ and $[90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_S$ of three-directional fibre composite laminates are also presented, where the suffix "S" shows the symmetry. These specimens are named C-4 and C-5, respectively. The mechanical properties of these specimens are shown in Table 1. The shape and dimension of test specimens are shown by Figure 1, in which the hold part of the specimen is reinforced by a GFRP tab.

Test method

The tensile test is done by an Instron-type testing machine at the rate of a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. The load-displacement curve is recorded by an X-Y recorder. The diagram of an AE measuring system (Shimadzu SAE 1000A) is shown by Figure 2. The AE signals detected from sensors are amplified by the preamplifier and amplified to 80 dB by the main amplifier through a high pass filter of 10 KHz, when the threshold value is set up at 500 mV. Moreover, the AE wave signals through the counter, the envelope and the A/D transformer are analyzed by a 16 bit personal computer with signals from a load-displacement curve. The ordinary AE parameters determined by

TABLE 1
Mechanical properties of specimens.

Specimen	Stacking sequence (deg.)	Elastic modulus E(GPa)	Tensile strength σ_B (MPa)	Poisson's ratio ν	Elongation ψ (%)
C-1	$[0]_8$	140	1600	0.24	6.0
C-2	$[45]_8$	14	81	0.24	1.1
C-3	$[90]_8$	11	46	0.03	0.7
C-4	$[0/\pm 45/90]_S$	54	520	0.25	3.4
C-5	$[90/\pm 45/0]_S$	53	600	0.28	3.6

Strain rate: 0.3%/min, Temp.: $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $60 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$

Figure 1. Shape and dimension of test specimen.

Figure 2. Block diagram of AE measuring system.

the AE measuring apparatus are the AE event count, the AE cumulative event count, the AE total energy and the AE amplitude distribution. In a frequency analysis, the AE signals are recorded on the data recorder (Sony Magnescape FMR-1219) and the power spectrum is determined by the AE wave for the analyzer (Analogic DATA 6000). There are sensors of two kinds, one is a resonance-type of 200~400 KHz for measuring the ordinary AE parameters and the other is a wide-range type for the frequency analysis. The two channels are used in a differential type to avoid noise in both tests. The fracture surfaces are observed by using a scanning electron microscope and an optical one for observing the fracture mechanisms of the conventional and laminated CFRP.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fracture mechanisms and the AE characteristics of unidirectional fibre composite laminates

Figure 3 shows the relation between the load-displacement curve, the AE cumulative event count and the AE total energy for C-1, C-2 and C-3 speci-

Figure 3. Load-displacement curve and AE characteristics (1) load, (2) AE cumulative event count and (3) AE total energy.

Figure 4. AE amplitude distribution of C-1, C-2 and C-3 specimens.

mens. The specimens fracture rapidly at the maximum load. However, comparing the fracture strength, it is found that the fracture strength is influenced by the fibre orientation and the structure of the reinforcement as the fracture strength of the C-1 specimen is higher than those of C-2 and C-3 specimens. The AE signals of C-1 specimen are generated at 12% of the maximum load, and increase with an increase in the load. The AE signals of C-2 specimen are generated at 17% of the maximum load and increase with an increase in load. The AE signals of C-3 specimen are generated at 20% of the maximum load and show the same tendency as the AE signals of C-2 specimen.

Figure 4 shows the AE amplitude distribution of C-1, C-2 and C-3 specimens, as it is important to investigate the distribution [4]. However, as the fracture mechanisms are a little different for each specimens from observation of microfractographs, it seems that the AE amplitude distributions show the same width, but it is difficult to determine the fracture mechanisms by only the AE amplitude distribution.

A typical example of an AE power spectrum of the specimens is shown by Figure 5, in which it seems that the peaks are 80 and 390 KHz, 160 KHz, 270 KHz and 390 KHz in Figures (a), (b), (c) and (d), respectively. It seems that the results mentioned above are similar to the frequencies and the fracture mechanisms obtained by microscopic observation of the model CFRP (3). Therefore, it is found that 80 KHz corresponds to the matrix fracture, 160 KHz to the fibre debonding, 270 KHz to the friction between the fibre and the matrix, and 390 KHz to the fibre breaking, respectively. Considering the experimental data scattering, it seems that the peaks of the AE spectra of the matrix fracture, the fibre debonding and the fibre breaking which contains the fibre friction between the broken fibre and the matrix are 50~100, 150~250 and 270~390 KHz, respectively.

The fracture mechanisms and the AE characteristics of three-directional fibre composite laminates

Figure 6 shows the relation between the load-displacement curve, the AE cumulative event and the total AE energy. In the C-4 specimen, the delaminations are generated between 90° layers or 45° and 90° layers at about 95% of the maximum load. When the delaminations generated from the both edges are connected, the specimen fractures at the maximum load. The AE signals are generated at a very low load level, but the AE cumulative event count and the total AE energy increase from the point at which the delamination initiates between the 90° layers or the 45° and 90° layers. It is observed in C-5 specimen that many cracks along the fibres in the 90° layer of the surface, (the crack is called the 90° layer crack hereafter), at 65% of the maximum load, although the AE signals are generated at a very low load level. However, the relation between the 90° layer cracks and the AE characteristics can not be investigated clearly, as it is difficult to measure the onset and the density of the 90° layer cracks.

It is found from the observation of microfractographs that a large quantity of matrix fractures, fibre debondings and fibre breakings on the delaminated surfaces. It seems that the delamination contains a fracture which have the matrix fracture, the fibre debonding and the fibre breaking. Figure 7 shows the AE amplitude at the delamination. The AE event counts distribute relatively at the higher amplitude side in the C-4 specimen. It is considered that the delamination initiates between the 90° layers or 90° and 45° layers when the load is about 85% of the maximum load, and the final

Figure 5. A typical example of an AE power spectrum of C-1, C-2 and C-3 specimens.

Figure 6. Load-displacement curve and AE characteristics (1) load, (2) AE cumulative event count and (3) AE total energy.

Figure 7. AE amplitude distribution at delamination of C-4 and C-5 specimens.

fracture occurs by the delamination. However, the AE event counts distribute relatively on the lower AE amplitude side in C-5 specimen. It is suggested that the 90° layer crack initiates in the 90° layer and the delamination initiates between 90° and 45° layers. As these specimens have the same constituent elements but the AE amplitude of both specimens differ from the sequence in laminate, this problem needs to be studied further in the future.

Figure 8 shows a typical example of an AE power spectrum of C-4 and C-5 specimens, in which figures (a), (b), (c) and (d) show the peaks of 70, 160, 390 and 630 KHz, respectively. The AE spectra of C-4 and C-5 specimens contain the same power spectra of C-4 and C-5 specimens. If the microfracture mechanisms of C-4 and C-5 specimens seem to be similar to the ones of C-1, C-2 and C-3 specimens, the relation between the AE power spectrum and the AE source of C-1, C-2 and C-3 specimens is applicable to the relations of C-4 and C-5 specimens. A large quantity of the matrix fracture (a), the fibre debonding (b) and the fibre breaking (c), in the power spectra are found during the delamination process. Considering these results with fracture mechanisms on fracture surfaces, the delamination process contains the spectra by friction [5] between fibres on two layers and it is considered that the frequency of 630 KHz is generated by the friction.

CONCLUSION

The conventional CFRP is investigated by tensile tests and measuring the AE waves. From the AE parameters and the observation of microfracture surfaces, the fracture mechanisms of conventional CFRP are studied in this paper. The results obtained are as follows:

- (1) Referring to the fracture mechanisms of model CFRP using the AE spectrum, the fracture mechanisms of conventional unidirectional carbon fibre composites are clarified; i.e. the peaks of the AE spectra of the matrix fracture, the fibre debonding and the fibre breaking, considering the experimental data scattering and the friction between the broken fibre and the matrix are 50~100, 150~250 and 270~390 KHz, respectively.
- (2) The AE amplitudes in the delamination of three-directional carbon fibre composite laminate $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ distribute a relatively higher amplitude side, while the AE amplitudes distribute a relatively lower amplitude side on the specimen $[90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_S$. As the AE amplitude distribution depends upon the sequence in the laminate, it is considered that the AE amplitude can not make the fracture mechanisms clear.
- (3) The results of fracture mechanisms of model CFRP by the carbon fibre composite laminates. However, the frequency of 630 KHz, the AE frequency spectrum is applicable to the three-directional, which is not generated in the AE frequency spectrum of model CFRP, is found in the three-directional carbon fibre composite laminates. It can be considered that the frequency of 630 KHz is generated by the friction between the fibres on the fracture surfaces.

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Figure 8. A typical example of an AE power spectrum of C-4 and C-5 specimens.

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